

Object Detection using SURF features

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Abstract

A common method for locating items in photos is object detection utilising the Speeded-Up Robust Features (SURF) algorithm. In order to identify the existence of a certain object, this method pulls important details from an image and compares them to a learned collection of features. The algorithm used in this method can identify items even when they are rotated or partially obscured. The SURF technique is particularly helpful in computer vision applications where object detection is crucial, such as facial recognition and autonomous vehicles. An overview of the SURF algorithm and its use in object detection is given in this abstract.

Keywords: Speeded -up Robust Feature Transform (SURF), Object Detection, Image processing.

1. Introduction

To find and identify things in an image, utilise the SURF (Speeded Up Robust Features) object identification method in MATLAB. A computer vision algorithm called SURF can be used to identify and match items in various images by extracting recognisable features from an image. The following steps are involved in object detection using MATLAB's SURF feature.

The SURF method is utilised for feature extraction from the image. These characteristics can withstand variations in lighting and viewpoint and are local and scale-invariant. Feature matching is the process of comparing the features that were extracted from the input image to the features of the target object. Finding the best connection between the features of the input image and the object is the goal of the matching procedure.

Localization of Objects: After the matching process is finished, it is possible to pinpoint where the object is located inside the input image.

SURF-based object detection is possible with built-in MATLAB tools. For feature extraction, the 'detectSURFFeatures' function is utilised, and for feature matching, the 'matchFeatures' function. The 'estimateGeometricTransform' function can be used to determine the transformation needed to align the item with the input image once the features have been matched.

2. Study Objectives

- SURF-based object detection is possible with built-in MATLAB tools. For feature extraction, the 'detectSURFFeatures' function is utilised, and for feature matching, the 'matchFeatures' function. The 'estimateGeometricTransform' function can be used to determine the transformation needed to align the item with the input image once the features have been matched.

The following are the main goals of using SURF features in object detection:

- **Robustness:** SURF characteristics are made to withstand variations in lighting and viewpoint, making them appropriate for object detection in real-world situations where these factors can fluctuate.
- **Scale-invariance:** SURF features can recognise and characterise features in the image at various scales because they are scale-invariant. They can therefore be used to identify items of various sizes in an image.
- **Being distinctive:** SURF features are made to be distinguishable, making it possible to match them precisely. They can therefore be helpful for precisely locating and recognising items in an image.

3. Methodology

The method for Detection of Object using SIFT features

- The methods used to detect the object in a cluster image is one of the feature matching technique which is known as SURF feature extraction. SURF(Speed-up Robust) is a one of the features used in a MATLAB software. In this project we use SURF feature to extract the matching point in a template image and source image.

3.1. Interior

- The SURF feature use a kernel to detect based on their matching. The sample image is divided into 3X3 matrix and also template image is divided into 3X3 matrix. The entire template image matrix.

3.2. Exterior

- *Step 1:* Firstly the template image is read through the MATLAB. It can be either real-time image or object. And source image is read where the template image's object is placed somewhere in the image. In our project we give staple remover as a template image and cluster desk as a source image. In our project we give staple remover as a template image and cluster desk as a source image. Page | 113
- *Step 2:* In second step take strongest feature point from the template image which is an staple remover box and take same as the staple remover for cluster desk image.
- *Step 2.1:* First take 25 strongest feature point from a Stapler remover image or template image, then take 50 strongest feature point from the Stapler remover image or template image. Then take 75 strongest feature point from the stapler remover or template image. And finally take 100 feature points from the template image or box image.
- *Step 2.2:* After completed the process of extraction of feature point on a Stapler remover image or template image its time to extract feature points from cluster image or source image. From the beginning , take 100 feature points , its because the no .of . bits in a source image is high compare with template image. Take till 300 feature points so that the amount of accuracy will high.
- *Step 3:* In next step putative matched point is taken in localized area from the template image with the source image and also in a globalized manner.
- *Step 4:* As a result , the object is been detected and indicated with the coloured square shape around the border of the template image.

4. Object Detection Using SIFT Feature

Figure.1. Cluster Image

In fig.1 shows the cluster image which has more than one image in a desk is will take it as a source image

Figure.2. Image of an Elephant

In fig 2 we take the Elephant as a Target image

Figure.3. Taking the 300 strongest point

In fig 3 we take the 100 strongest point from the Target image by pointing out the highest point where the intensity level is maximum from the image

Figure.4. Taking putative points in globally

In fig 4 we take the putative point in both compare with the target image and source image

5. Future Directions

1. The Speeded-Up Robust Features (SURF) algorithm has proven to be a successful approach for object detection in computer vision. The method can yet be enhanced for new object detection applications. The following are some potential future prospects for SURF-based object detection:
2. Integration of deep learning Two deep learning-based object recognition methods, YOLO and Faster R-CNN, have shown remarkable outcomes. Future research can focus on integrating SURF characteristics with deep learning models to improve the accuracy and resilience of object detection.
3. Improved feature extraction: SURF features may not always be the best option for all photos, despite their resistance to changes in scale and rotation. Future studies might look into ways to enhance feature extraction techniques that can be combined with SURF to enhance object detection.
4. Object detection in real time can be difficult since the SURF approach can be computationally expensive. The goal of future research might be to accelerate SURF-based object detection.

6. Conclusion

In computer vision applications, the Speeded-Up Robust Features (SURF) algorithm has proven to be a trustworthy method for object detection. Nevertheless, there is still opportunity for advancement and a number of potential routes for SURF-based object detection in the future.

Future work might look into how to combine SURF with deep learning techniques, improve the robustness of SURF to occlusion, extend SURF to multi-class object detection, enhance feature extraction techniques, and investigate the use of SURF-based object detection in robotic systems.

Overall, SURF is a potent object detection technology that has proven successful in a variety of applications. Researchers can further enhance the precision and effectiveness of SURF-based object detection by pursuing new approaches and strategies, opening the door to cutting-edge computer vision technologies.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Lowe, D. G. (2004). Distinctive image features from scale-invariant keypoints. *International journal of computer vision*, 60(2), 91-110.
- [2]. Bay, H., Tuytelaars, T., & Van Gool, L. (2006). Surf: Speeded up robust features. In *European conference on computer vision* (pp. 404-417). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- [3]. Mikolajczyk, K., & Schmid, C. (2005). A performance evaluation of local descriptors. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 27(10), 1615-1630.
- [4]. Nister, D., & Stewenius, H. (2006). Scalable recognition with a vocabulary tree. In *2006 IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR'06)* (Vol. 2, pp. 2161-2168). IEEE.
- [5]. Wang, X., Han, T. X., & Yan, S. (2007). An HOG-LBP human detector with partial occlusion handling. In *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition* (pp. 1-8).
- [6]. Liu, Y., Lu, J., & Zhang, H. J. (2012). Object detection via selective sparse reconstruction. In *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition* (pp. 1878-1885).
- [7]. Dalal, N., & Triggs, B. (2005). Histograms of oriented gradients for human detection. In *2005 IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR'05)* (Vol. 1, pp. 886-893). IEEE.
- [8]. Wang, J., & Ji, Q. (2011). SIFT-based object recognition with application to face recognition. In *Computer vision and pattern recognition workshops (CVPRW), 2011 IEEE computer society conference on* (pp. 26-33). IEEE.